

Preliminary Investigation on Cashew Nut Shell Polysaccharides*

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Although a number of reports¹⁻⁴ have appeared on the structure of gum exuded by "cashew" tree (*Anacardium occidentale*), the polysaccharide constituents of cashew nut shells have remained uninvestigated so far. The present communication deals with the isolation and preliminary investigation of two polysaccharides occurring in the roasted cashew nut shells.

The preparative procedure of the two polysaccharides is schematically represented below.

Roasted cashew shell powder, after being defatted by refluxing with petroleum ether, b.p. 80-100° for 24 hrs. was extracted with cold water to obtain the water soluble polysaccharide (I). The defatted material was delignified by repeated treatment with sodium hypochlorite solution (0.7%) and the hemicellulose was extracted with caustic soda solution of increasing concentrations. A maximum yield of Hemicellulose B was obtained from 5% caustic soda extract after acidification and pouring in ethanol.

Purification of the water soluble polysaccharide (I) was carried out by treatment with freshly regenerated cation exchange resin, Duolite C-25. Final precipitation with ethanol furnished compound (I) in a pure state in the form of a white powder having a low ash content (sulphated ash, 0.45%). The compound did not reduce Fehling's solution

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3. Smith and Montgomery. "The chemistry of plant gums and mucilages", Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1959, p. 315.
4. Biswas and Bose, *Science and Culture*, 1966, 32, 134.

and on analysis give Furfural, 6.27, Pentogen, 10.8, Pentoses 12.06 percent, Eq. Wt., 1650. Nitrogen, sulphur, halogens and methoxyl were found to be absent in (I). Though its aqueous solution was acidic in nature (*pH*, 3.1), (I) did not undergo autohydrolysis even when heated on a steam bath for 80 hrs. It however underwent complete hydrolysis when heated with sulphuric acid (*N*) for forty hours. The hydrolysate, after neutralisation with barium carbonate, was concentrated to a syrup and extracted exhaustively with dry methanol to furnish two fractions, (i) a mixture of neutral sugars and (ii) an uronic acid in the form of barium salt (Ba, 26.1; calc. for barium hexuronate, $(C_6H_7O_7)_2$, Ba, require Ba, 26.5 per cent). Chromatographic resolution of the neutral sugar mixture on filter paper as well as on a cellulose column gave rise to three sugars, L-rhamnose, L-arabinose and D-galactose which were finally identified from their specific rotations and m.p. of their characteristic crystalline derivatives. The free uronic acid did not carry a methoxyl group and was identified as D-galacturonic acid from the following considerations. When treated with (i) basic lead acetate⁵ and (ii) cysteine hydrochloride and concentrated sulphuric acid⁶, it developed pink and greenish blue colour respectively characteristic of galacturonic acid. Paper chromatography of the uronic acid using non-aqueous phase of *n*-butanol-acetic acid—water (4:1:5) as developer and *p*-anisidine hydrochloride spray reagent furnished a single pink spot and not two⁷, indicative of the absence of glucuronic acid. Finally, the methyl ester, methyl glycoside of the uronic acid was reduced with sodium borohydride and hydrolysed with acid when only D-galactose was obtained and identified. A quantitative hydrolysis of (i) indicated that the three neutral sugars were present in the proportion of 1:2:17.

Purification of hemicellulose B (Compound II) by reprecipitation followed by extraction of the precipitated material with aqueous ethanol (50%) and ethanol⁸ resulted in the production of a white powder (sulphated ash, 0.74%). This, upon complete hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (*N*) and subsequent treatment yielded D-galacturonic acid and a neutral sugar mixture consisting of D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-galactose. The identification of the uronic acid and neutral sugars was carried out in the same manner as described earlier. In the acid hydrolysis experiment, it was observed that the yield of uronic acid was much less as compared to that of the neutral sugar. This indicates that the uronic acid content of the hemicellulose should be low. Direct determination of the anhydro-uronic acid content of the hemicellulose (A.U.A., 6.2%) by the modified procedure of Mc Cready and coworkers⁹ corroborates the above observation. Further, studies on the structure of the water soluble polysaccharide (I) and hemicellulose (II) are in progress.

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